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A Dual-Mode Retrieval-Augmented Generation System for Interactive Question Answering of Public Tender Documents

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Abstract

This paper presents a Retrieval-Augmented Generation (RAG) system for question answering over the set of documents of a public tender. The proof-of-concept chatbot is intended to provide support to officers participating in the evaluation process of a tender whose documents are indexed. The system implements a dual-mode retrieval strategy —supporting both semantic and lexical search— to extract relevant context and uses an instruction-following language model to generate grounded responses based strictly on the retrieved information. The system is designed to assist officers in exploring tenders, evaluation reports, and award justifications through natural language queries. In order to assess the system, the documents of a tender have been generated synthetically. Qualitative testing demonstrated that the system provided accurate, verifiable answers, avoiding unsupported inferences. The architecture emphasizes document fidelity, interpretability, and usability for non-technical users involved in procurement oversight. Future work may extend the framework to support the identification of fraud-related patterns.

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1. Introduction

Public procurement accounts for a significant share of governmental spending and, as such, constitutes a domain subject to scrutiny and highly susceptible to inefficiencies, collusion, and fraud. Among these concerns, bid rigging—a collusive practice in which suppliers manipulate competition by coordinating their bids—poses a persistent challenge for regulatory bodies and oversight institutions. Detection of such practices is often hindered by the complexity, volume and unstructured nature of procurement documents, making manual review both inefficient and unreliable.

To address this analytical bottleneck, a Retrieval-Augmented Generation (RAG) system was developed to support interactive exploration of public procurement documents. The system enables users—such as public officers, auditors, or compliance analysts—to analyze the documents of a tender by asking natural language questions and receiving grounded answers based on the content of the documents. Although the system does not perform automated detection of collusive practices, it facilitates the identification of relevant information that may indicate irregularities, thereby assisting users in their investigative efforts.

A distinguishing feature of the proposed system is its dual-mode retrieval design, which allows users to choose between semantic and lexical search strategies depending on the nature of their query. This flexibility is intended to support both conceptually phrased questions and exact-match lookups involving keywords, codes, or legal terms, where lexical search is more effective. The lexical retrieval component is based on the Whoosh search engine, which is a lightweight, pure-Python library for full-text indexing and search [1]. Whoosh supports tokenization, inverted indexing, and TF-IDF scoring and was selected for its ease of integration and suitability for small- to medium-scale document corpora. In contrast, the semantic retrieval component employs dense vector representations and similarity search through FAISS, thereby enabling the identification of conceptually related content even in the absence of exact term overlap. Although not formally evaluated in terms of retrieval metrics, the proposed dual-mode design was found to be useful for adapting to different types of document content and question styles.

The architecture is optimized for the Spanish language, incorporating domain-adapted linguistic processing to support analysis in jurisdictions in which Spanish is the primary administrative language. Furthermore, the system has been implemented as a functional prototype and is deployed through an interactive graphical interface, which facilitates document ingestion, user query formulation, and real-time response generation. This interface is designed to provide accessible interaction with the underlying RAG pipeline, making it a practical tool for analysts, auditors, and legal professionals.

The primary contributions of this work are summarized as follows:

- The design and implementation of a domain-specific RAG system for question-answering of procurement documents, supporting information extraction relevant to the risk assessment of bid rigging.
- The integration and comparison of lexical (Whoosh) and semantic (FAISS-based) retrieval methods, highlighting their complementary strengths.
- An efficient architecture that utilizes quantized transformer-based language models [2] and sentence-level embeddings to realize responsive performance on standard hardware.
- A user-accessible application layer that supports nontechnical users in document exploration and analysis.

This paper presents the system architecture, underlying methodology, and a representative case study illustrating the system's applicability to public procurement oversight. To frame the scope of the study, we focus on three core research questions: whether a Retrieval-Augmented Generation (RAG) system can provide accurate, document-grounded answers to natural language queries over Spanish-language procurement documents; how the integration of semantic and lexical retrieval contributes to the relevance and interpretability of the responses; and whether it can help non-technical users extract procedural and evaluative information reliably.

2. Related Work

The task of analyzing public procurement data to detect irregularities such as bid rigging intersects with multiple research domains, including information retrieval, natural language processing, and computational legal studies. Traditional methods for reviewing procurement documents have relied heavily on manual inspection or rule-based systems, which are often constrained by limitations in scalability and adaptability.

In the area of information retrieval, keyword-based approaches remain prevalent in legacy systems used by public sector institutions. Such systems, while efficient for exact term matching, typically lack the capacity to capture semantic nuances or contextual variations in legal and administrative language. Text search engines like Whoosh and Lucene, offer robust indexing and querying capabilities based on term frequency–inverse document frequency (TF-IDF) schemes; however, they may be limited in cases where synonyms, paraphrasing, or implicit references are common.

Recent advances in semantic retrieval have attempted to address these limitations using dense vector representations of text. Sentence-transformer models trained for semantic similarity tasks [3] allow for the embedding of text into high-dimensional vector spaces, facilitating retrieval based on meaning rather than surface form. FAISS (Facebook AI Similarity Search) has become a standard tool for scalable approximate nearest-neighbor search in such embeddings [4].

Building on these foundations, Retrieval-Augmented Generation (RAG) architectures have emerged as effective frameworks for question answering over document collections. These systems retrieve relevant context from external sources and integrate it into the prompt of a generative language model, thereby enabling grounded and context-aware responses. Notable applications include OpenAI’s GPT-based tools, Meta’s RAG model [5], and hybrid systems tailored to specific domains, such as healthcare [6] and legal compliance [7].

In recent years, the application of NLP to public procurement analysis has also gained attention. Studies have explored the use of machine learning for anomaly detection in bid patterns, pricing irregularities, and supplier networks [8]. For instance, a supervised learning framework has been proposed to flag irregular tendering behavior using structured procurement data across European countries [9]. Explainable AI techniques have also been applied to the auditing of public procurement contracts, using a combination of statistical and language models to detect and interpret spurious textual patterns associated with potentially fraudulent behavior [10]. Additionally, text mining and NLP techniques have been employed to extract structured metadata from large-scale procurement documents, supporting risk analysis and contract monitoring in multilingual public sector environments [11].

These contributions demonstrate the increasing relevance of AI techniques in public procurement oversight and highlight the potential of domain-specific tools to support auditing, compliance verification, and data extraction from complex administrative records.

3. System Architecture

The proposed Retrieval-Augmented Generation (RAG) system comprises five primary components: (1) document ingestion and preprocessing, (2) chunking and indexing, (3) dual-mode retrieval, (4) language generation, and (5) user interface.

Illustration 1 Design of the System Architecture

3.1. Document Ingestion and Preprocessing

The system accepts multiple document formats, including PDF, plain text (TXT), and comma-separated values (CSV). Uploaded files are parsed using format-specific routines: PDF documents were read using PyPDF2, plain text files were decoded as UTF-8, and CSV files were ingested with pandas. The extracted content was concatenated into a unified text stream.

To facilitate accurate text interpretation in Spanish, the system incorporates the *es_core_news_sm* model from *spaCy*. This enables linguistic preprocessing—including tokenization and sentence segmentation—tailored to the syntactic and morphological characteristics of Spanish-language administrative documents.

3.2. Chunking and Indexing

The preprocessing stage is followed by a paragraph-aware segmentation procedure. Instead of fixed-size word windows, the system identifies paragraph blocks and groups them into coherent fragments of approximately 500–800 characters. This approach improves semantic distinctiveness across chunks and minimizes redundancy.

Two indexing strategies are applied independently:

- Semantic indexing is performed by encoding each chunk using the paraphrase-multilingual-MiniLM-L12-v2 sentence transformer. Embeddings are normalized to unit length and indexed with FAISS (IndexFlatIP) to enable efficient inner-product similarity search.
- Lexical indexing uses the Whoosh engine, a lightweight full-text search library implemented in Python. Each chunk is assigned a unique identifier and indexed within a TF-IDF-based schema, thereby enabling keyword-style retrieval based on literal term matching.

3.3. Dual-Mode Retrieval

The system supports two mutually exclusive retrieval modes upon receiving a user query:

- The semantic retrieval encodes the query using the same sentence transformer and performs a nearest-neighbor search over the FAISS index, thereby returning the most semantically relevant chunks.
- Lexical retrieval parses the query using Whoosh’s query parser and identifies the top-matching fragments based on literal token overlap and TF-IDF scoring.

In both modes, the top-ranked fragments are displayed to the user for transparency and are then passed to the language generation module for response construction.

3.4. Language Generation

The generation component is powered by *mistralai/Mistral-7B-Instruct-v0.2*, which is a transformer-based language model tuned for instruction. The model was loaded with 4-bit quantization using the *BitsAndBytes* library to reduce GPU memory consumption and support efficient inference on professional-grade hardware. Text generation was handled through a Hugging Face transformer pipeline configured for deterministic output. Retrieved fragments are inserted into a structured prompt template designed to constrain the model to document-grounded responses. The short-term conversational context is preserved to support multiturn interactions and follow-up queries.

All experiments were conducted on a workstation equipped with two NVIDIA RTX 4000 Ada Generation GPUs (20 GB VRAM each), running under CUDA 12.8 and driver version 570.124.06. During inference, the system used approximately 5–6 GB of GPU memory per instance. This setup provides responsive real-time performance while maintaining compatibility with accessible high-end hardware configurations.

3.5. User Interface and Interaction

A web-based interface is implemented using Streamlit, which allows users to upload documents, select retrieval modes, pose questions, and view generated answers. The sidebar displays file management and system state tracking, while the main panel displays the chat interface, query controls, retrieved evidence, and conversation history.

The design prioritizes usability for non-technical users, including auditors, investigators, and analysts engaged in public procurement oversight.

Illustration 1. Web interface design

4. Methodology

The methodology employed in this study centers on applying the RAG system to public tenders documents in order to assist users in extracting information relevant to the analysis of potentially collusive bidding behavior. The operational pipeline combines system-level configurations with task-specific strategies to ensure the reliability and interpretability of the results.

4.1. Dual-Mode Retrieval Strategy

Given the variability in the tender document structure and terminology, the system supports two mutually exclusive retrieval modes: lexical and semantic. Lexical retrieval is implemented using the Whoosh search engine and is available to users for exact-match queries involving keywords such as company names, procurement codes, or legal clauses. In contrast, semantic retrieval leverages dense vector representations computed with the paraphrase-multilingual-MiniLM-L12-v2 model and retrieves conceptually related fragments via similarity search using FAISS.

Although both retrieval options are part of the system architecture, the evaluation presented in this study primarily reflects the use of semantic retrieval, which was more aligned with the natural language query patterns examined. In particular, the semantic approach demonstrated advantages when handling paraphrased or abstract formulations—such as indirect references to procedural decisions or supplier characteristics.

The adoption of a more expressive embedding model also contributed to improved retrieval diversity, reducing the recurrence of identical top-k fragments and enhancing the contextual variability of the retrieved results.

4.2. Use Case Framing and Prompting Design

Prompts were designed to support tasks typically performed by knowledgeable analysts reviewing complex procurement documents. Rather than detecting collusive behavior, the system helps users explore contracts, evaluation reports, and administrative resolutions through interactive queries. The objective is to extract relevant, document-grounded information—such as evaluation criteria, awarded amounts, supplier documentation, and procedural justifications.

The prompt structure was designed to prioritize traceability and reduce speculative output. Embedded instructions discourage unsupported inference and require the language model to base its answers strictly on the retrieved fragments. This design aligns with the expectations of legal and administrative review, where precision, verifiability, and accountability are paramount.

The inclusion of short-term conversational contexts enables multiturn interaction. For example, a user might inquire about the awarded amount and then follow up with a question about the justification or evaluation breakdown, progressively constructing a fuller understanding of the procurement case.

The prompt template was designed to constrain the model's generative behavior to ensure that answers remained faithful to the retrieved content. The model was explicitly instructed to avoid repeating the question, refrain from unsupported speculation, and not copy document fragments verbatim. Retrieved chunks were prefixed as a bullet-pointed list under the “Document fragments” section, followed by the conversation history (if present), and then the current question. A final instruction block reinforced the rules for text generation and emphasized that the model should only provide an answer if sufficient evidence was found in the fragments. The prompt structure was refined through iterative testing to ensure document fidelity.

4.3. Document and Query Selection

To explore the system's behavior under realistic conditions, a set of synthetic tender documents was used. These documents were generated using a large language model and carefully curated to emulate the structure and language of real-world administrative texts in Spanish. The corpus included simulated tender notices, bidder lists, evaluation reports, award resolutions, and contract justifications. While not derived from a formal dataset, the content was designed to resemble authentic procurement materials in tone, layout, and informational scope.

Users' queries were developed to reflect typical information needs encountered by auditors, analysts, or legal reviewers working with such documents. Rather than detecting fraud or collusion, the proposed system was tested for its ability to extract specific factual and procedural information in response to natural language questions.

The queries used in testing were originally developed in Spanish, reflecting realistic investigative questions that analysts might pose when reviewing procurement documents. The following are representative examples with their English translations:

- **ES:** *¿Cuál fue el monto total adjudicado?* **EN:** *What was the total awarded amount?*
- **ES:** *¿Qué empresa obtuvo el mayor puntaje en la evaluación?* **EN:** *Which company received the highest score in the evaluation?*
- **ES:** *¿Se menciona justificación para adjudicación directa?* **EN:** *Is there any justification mentioned for a direct award?*
- **ES:** *¿Qué criterios de evaluación se utilizaron?* **EN:** *What evaluation criteria were used?*
- **ES:** *¿Hubo empresas que no cumplieron con los requisitos técnicos?* **EN:** *Were there any companies that failed to meet the technical requirements?*

These examples were chosen to verify whether the system could provide relevant, document-grounded responses without introducing hallucinated content, thereby supporting document understanding tasks rather than automated judgment.

5. Case Study and Evaluation

To assess the effectiveness of the proposed system in supporting document-grounded analysis, a qualitative evaluation was conducted using the synthetic procurement documents described in the previous section. The goal was to determine whether the system could accurately retrieve relevant fragments and generate faithful responses to realistic information needs posed in natural language. For illustrative purposes, the original Spanish-language queries used during testing have been translated into English in the following table.

Table 1: Examples of qualitative evaluation of the proposed system

Query (EN)	System Response (Semantic via FA)	Fragment Source
Which company achieved the highest evaluation score?	The company ElectroSur SA received the highest score in the evaluation, with 93 points.	Evaluation report
What is the total awarded amount?	The total amount awarded to ElectroSur SA was €1,180,000.	Award resolution
Is there any justification for a direct award?	The document states that the direct award was not justified.	Justification memo
What evaluation criteria were used?	The evaluation criteria were price (40%), technical experience (30%), and proposed execution time (30%).	Tender notice
Are there companies that failed to meet the technical requirements?	According to the report, Alumbrar Servicios did not present the required electrical safety certifications.	Evaluation report
Which supplier provided the shortest execution time?	Alumbrar Servicios offers a completion time of 60 days.	Bidder list
Were any irregularities detected in the evaluation?	No information was found in the document regarding irregularities in the evaluation.	Evaluation report

The proposed system supports both semantic and lexical retrieval modes; however, all results presented in Table 1 were obtained using the semantic retrieval configuration. Lexical retrieval via Whoosh remains available as an alternative to exact-match queries; however, it was not included in the scope of this paper.

6. Discussion

The system developed in this study demonstrates the feasibility and practical value of applying Retrieval-Augmented Generation (RAG) techniques to interactive analysis of public procurement documents. Through the combination of semantic and lexical retrieval options with instruction-tuned language generation, the system enables users to pose natural language queries and receive grounded answers based on heterogeneous and often unstructured administrative texts.

Several key lessons emerged from the development and evaluation of the proposed model:

- **Prompt fidelity and fragment grounding are critical.** Early iterations of the system showed that excessive fragment compression or deduplication could lead to hallucinated or incomplete answers. The full preservation of retrieved chunks significantly improved contextual fidelity and output quality.
- **Embedding and chunking strategies affect retrieval diversity.** The use of semantically expressive embeddings paired with paragraph-aware chunking helped mitigate the repetition of top-k fragments and increased the variety of context provided to the language model.
- **Semantic retrieval was better suited to exploratory queries.** All responses reported in the evaluation relied on semantic retrieval via FAISS, which proved effective for paraphrased or indirect questions. Lexical retrieval using Whoosh remains available in the system for exact-match scenarios; however, it was not formally evaluated in this study.
- **The model and embedder selection significantly influence the retrieval and generation quality.** The use of an instruction-tuned language model along with a semantically expressive embedding model (MiniLM-L12-v2) contributed to improvements in both fragment diversity and answer precision. This highlights the importance of architectural alignment between the retrieval pipeline and the generative model to ensure coherent, document-grounded outputs.
- **Evaluation with synthetic data limits generalizability.** While it enabled controlled experimentation, synthetic documents do not fully reflect the complexity and variability of real-world procurement records.

This may affect retrieval accuracy and answer fidelity. Future work should include authentic tenders to validate system performance under operational conditions.

- **The proposed system assists but does not replace human analysis.** It has proved helpful in extracting key information but it does not detect fraud or collusion. Answers are limited to the content of the documents and the specificity of the questions. Interpretative tasks are the responsibility of the human reviewer.

Overall, the system offers a responsive and accessible tool for supporting document-grounded investigation in public procurement oversight. The remaining challenges include scaling up large document collections, enabling multi-document reasoning, and exploring the integration of behavioral risk indicators in future extensions.

7. Conclusion

This work presents a Retrieval-Augmented Generation (RAG) system specifically tailored to assist in the analysis of Spanish-language public procurement documents. The proposed system combines two distinct retrieval modes—semantic and lexical—with prompt-constrained language generation to support natural language querying over heterogeneous and unstructured administrative texts.

Rather than automating the detection of collusive behavior, the system is designed to assist analysts, auditors, and oversight professionals in exploring procurement records, extracting relevant information, and navigating complex contractual documentation. Through architectural decisions such as paragraph-aware chunking, multilingual semantic embeddings, and the integration of an instruction-following language model, the system generates reliable and interpretable responses across a wide range of realistic investigative questions.

Qualitative testing confirmed the system’s ability to provide document-grounded answers with high fidelity while avoiding unsupported or speculative content. These results highlight the system’s value as a practical tool for information extraction and document review in public sector oversight settings.

While future extensions could explore multi-document reasoning or the incorporation of risk-related features, the current system already contributes to transparency and accountability in public procurement by enabling more accessible, efficient and informed document analysis.

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